

ON THE VALENCE OF THE WORD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10893753>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 20-March 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 25- March 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 29- March 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

valence, agent, addressee, class, sememe, tool.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the concept of valence, which is relevant in the study of syntagmatic relations of words in linguistics, and the issues related to its study in Uzbek linguistics are analyzed. Also, the scientific-theoretical views of Professor M.M. Mirtojiev, a linguist who has been conducting research on valence theory for many years, have been explained.

Analyzing the syntagmatic relationship of words, Professor M. Mirtojiev comments on the concept of valency: the combination of lexemes in the speech chain is their syntagmatic relationship. The lexical meaning of the word makes it possible to find the most necessary part - the word - for this word to enter into a combination in the structure of the sentence. The possibility of a word based on this particular lexical meaning is its valence. More precisely, valency is the possibility of combining with a certain word based on the specific lexical meaning of the word.

M. Mirtojiev studies the semantic valences of the Uzbek word by dividing it into four types:

- 1) lexical-semantic valency;
- 2) form semantics valence;
- 3) mediated semantic valence;
- 4) logical-semantic valency.

The lexical-semantic valence is defined according to the specific lexical meaning of the word, the instrumental semantic valence is defined by the actant of place or object valence with the word directly controlled by it, the valence of form semantics is defined according to the semantics of a morphological form of the word, and shows the logical-semantic valency as the valences that occur according to the logic of the denotation of the lexical meaning of the word¹.

Lexical-semantic valency begins with the lexical meaning of the word, that is, the sememe of the lexeme². This valence is observed in all the words of the group. It is especially active in sentences related to the verb group. M.Mirtojiev gives the following example: the

¹ Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. - Тошкент: Мумтоз сўз, 2010. - 235 б.

² Schippan Th. Einführung in die Scmasiologic. - S.30 IT, 91ff.

class of the combination of keldi in the tram and the combination of the knife in the knife have the same motor expression. But the verb "came" is a tool, and the verb "késdi" has the object-weapon valence.

In Turkic languages, including Uzbek, word valence is based not only on semantics, but also on semantics of form³. Such semantic valences are considered form semantic valences. Professor M.Mirtojiyev noted that this is observed in words of the verb, adjective and noun groups, especially when they are used as participles⁴: ... now I'm getting old myself (A. Mukhtar). In this sentence, the agent valence of the adjective participle "I am old" is expressed in the personal pronoun "myself".

Mediated semantic valence is when a word is semantically connected with an actant of a certain valence through an actant of another valence. Such valency exists in the Uzbek language as well as in other languages. It is observed especially when a word belonging to the verb family is used as participle. The scientist emphasizes that the participle verb directly controls a part of the sentence syntactically, without being semantically connected with it, i.e. not having a classema, but it is semantically connected through the actant of another valence of this verb. For this purpose, if we pay attention to the device that the person who ate went to the kitchen, it becomes clear that the actant of the target valence of the verb bord in the combination of the person who has eaten has no semantic connection with the word that he has eaten. However, the combination has syntactic integrity and is in the control connection. The verb has its locative valence actant with the word "kitchen" to form a class according to the educational system. The word "to the kitchen" has the same educational meaning as the word "to eat". In this case, the verb to go has a chain classema, in which the actant of the target valence forms a semantic link with the actant of the place valence through the word kitchen. Therefore, it is not considered lexical-semantic, but instrumental semantic valency⁵.

Professor M. Mirtojiyev does not reveal the logical-semantic valence based on the semantic structure of the lexical meaning of the word, i.e. the semes, but it appears depending on the essence of the lexical meaning, taking into account the concepts dialectically related to it in the objective existence, and accordingly He explains that he will have. For example, from the point of view of philosophy, a being in the objective world lives in a certain space, and does not exist outside of it. Also, each thing has its own sign, and the sign is reflected in the thing. Based on these, words carry valence and enter into communication through it. Such a valence is observed in Uzbek words belonging to the noun family. For example: Beautiful tulips, blue grass everywhere (Oybek). In this sentence, the nouns tulips and grasses act as participles, and their locative valence

is expressed in the word "everywhere". The noun participle and the actant of place do not have a common

³ Бу фикр дастлаб В.Л. Каримжонова томонидан илгари сурилди. Каримжонова В. А. Ўзбек тилида ўрин келишкли бирикмалар семантикаси. - 42-6.

⁴ Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. - Тошкент: Мумтоз сўз, 2010. – 237 б.

⁵ Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. - Тошкент: Мумтоз сўз, 2010. – 239 б

connecting theme, but the habitat of tulips and meadows is logically the same. It is represented by a noun formed with a locative case and syntactically acts as a locative⁶.

Phrases Valence classification	Noun	Adjective	Number	Pronoun	Adverb	Verb
Agent	√	√			√	√
Object	√	√			√	√
Content	√	√			√	√
Addressee	√	√			√	√
Place	√	√				√
Weapon						√
Reason		√				√
Tool	√					√
Status		√				√

A specific form of word semantic valence is verb valence. An important aspect of verb valence is that the verb determines the structure of the sentence. The verb is characterized by the carrier of valence in the sentence, the fact that it is the most basic constructive unit with the ability to attach other words to itself.

The subject, object, content, addressee, place, weapon, cause, means, condition valences of the word are lexical-semantic valence.

Among the word valences, the goal, quantity, and cause valence of the verb is the instrumental semantic valence.

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⁶ Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. – Тошкент: Мумтоз сўз, 2010. – 239 б

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